

THE BENEFITS OF THE GAME METHOD IN CHINESE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *A few features of using games to teach Chinese in the classroom are covered in the article. Games are unquestionably a fantastic approach to keep students motivated, aid in the gradual acquisition of vocabulary and grammar, and support the successful introduction of new material. Azart sparks a student's curiosity, which in turn propels advancement. The youngster advances to new language learning levels as a result of studying the content through the game and developing the idea that learning Chinese is a lot of fun.*

Keywords: *game activity; game teaching methods; Chinese language, Chinese lessons, school children, elementary Chinese language teaching, methods of teaching Chinese, lexical games, school textbooks, teaching games, game exercises, mysterious hieroglyphs and interesting methods.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИГРОВОГО МЕТОДА В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ КИТАЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются некоторые особенности использования игр для обучения китайскому языку в классе. Игры, несомненно, являются фантастическим подходом для поддержания мотивации студентов, помогают в постепенном приобретении словарного запаса и грамматики и способствуют успешному введению нового материала. Азарт разжигает любопытство студента, что, в свою очередь, стимулирует прогресс. Юноша переходит на новые уровни изучения языка в результате изучения содержания через игру и развития идеи, что изучение китайского языка — это очень весело.*

Ключевые слова: *игровая деятельность; игровые методы обучения; китайский язык, уроки китайского языка, школьники, начальное обучение китайскому языку, методы обучения китайскому языку, лексические игры, школьные учебники, обучающие игры, игровые упражнения, загадочные иероглифы и интересные методы.*

Introduction. The first years of school complicated by the fact that children are included in the educational process, far from always accompanied by a game, as in kindergarten. The study of new material is undoubtedly a complex type of activity, associated with a concentration on the subject, self-organization, and discipline. Due to this the acquisition of strong language skills in the process of educational activity and the choice of effective methods for mastering educational material is one of the urgent problems of teaching in elementary school. As A. S. Belkin rightly notes: "The game does not disappear from the life of the child - it is pushed into the background, still occupying a significant place, but educational activity acquires the main role". The introduction of the elements of the game in the lessons of language teaching contributes to a more successful process of mastering new concepts and the study of the subject.

The child's age, psychological makeup, and unique traits must all be considered by the teacher. The groundwork for understanding both native and foreign languages is established in

elementary school. Cognitive activity, which is included into activities that perfectly match the age features of kids in primary school, is fertile ground for this. The difficulty of successfully integrating lexical games into the teaching of foreign languages in secondary school primary grades is the focus of this study.

Methods. According to A.V. Konyshева, the game is a unique means of teaching a foreign language. “The game is synthetic because It is both the method and the form of organization of training. In addition, it synthesizes almost all methods of active learning”. Furthermore, educational games are games created by teachers using methodological tools and used during classes for teaching and raising children, focused on the sphere of proximal development of students. The game combines the pedagogical goal with an exciting motive for the child. Training games are different from other types of games with their substantial basis. In our educational activity, we rely on the concept of teaching games by M.F. Stranin, who highlights “preparatory games that contribute to the formation of speech skills (this group includes lexical, phonetic, spelling and grammatical) and creative games, the purpose of which is to further develop speech skills and skills”.

The usefulness of studying foreign languages is rising at the moment. The world has changed, impacting not just international politics, economy, and society at large but also the educational system. A second foreign language is now optionally studied in many schools in addition to English. These languages used to be Spanish and Italian, but now he is highly well-known in Chinese. The majority of parents believe it to be the language of the future, and kids in elementary schools find “mysterious hieroglyphs” intriguing.

Consider about the matter of teaching Chinese in schools. Chinese is undoubtedly one of the hardest languages in the world to learn. Additionally, studying becomes an engaging activity for students if an adult goes to it consciously and sets goals and objectives for himself. Mysterious hieroglyphs that are accompanied by intriguing images draw them in. This does not always match reality, though. Everything changes and the learner loses interest in the language as soon as he starts studying hieroglyphs.

Discussions and Results. Notwithstanding the foregoing, Uzbekistan continues to see Chinese as an unusual language. It is also not difficult to choose a teacher who would work with adults in classes or at a university; on the other hand, selecting a teacher who would deal with children (and occasionally with elementary school kids) is more challenging. Furthermore, a significant issue for educators is the availability of engaging, colorful, and stimulating textbooks for students, as well as the absence of textbook coherence within classes.

Another point of view is that, since visual memory is superior to text memory, it is a useful tool for teaching Chinese to students through engaging and interesting activities. Learners will remain calm and find it easier to retain the terms and concepts if they are not bored with the material being taught. Using games to teach is a good idea because it can pique students' interest and help them learn.

There may be pauses between classes, according to some lecturers, so that pupils can unwind. However, its purpose is not analogous to the game's adjustment. Teachers can resume teaching after the games since the pupils have calmed down and become more comfortable. The effectiveness of studying Mandarin Chinese is currently quite high. Children's favorite activity is

playing games. To some extent, students who start learning Chinese in China are also considered "children" in the language. These days, a wide range of entertainment is employed in several industries. As a result, it is reasonable and possible to incorporate games into Chinese instruction to improve student retention and the learning environment.

Teachers that can help students create an image, a process, or an event in every class will help students' brains develop, which will improve their memory. After the rigorous listening and pronunciation exercises, it is common for individuals who are just starting to study Mandarin to feel exhausted. There are various game styles. However, educators ought to put some effort into creating engaging games that support Chinese language learning for their pupils. Better still, if they could participate in the games. Teachers have an obligation to assist students in learning through play, not only play itself. To effectively support students' learning, teachers must be skilled in the teaching arts. Learning Chinese is a challenge for the majority of students that study there.

The phenomena of language are varied and intricate. To make things easier for students to accept and learn, teachers should reduce them into soothing lesson plans. They will thus acquire self-assurance and a greater interest in studying Chinese.

It is also important to mention that, maintaining a student's motivation is the primary responsibility of the teacher. You require a high level of focus, persistence, and creative thinking – yes, even fantasy – to acquire the Chinese language. Students have a complete order when working with fantasy, but if they are persistent and focused... Elementary school students focus more on outward activities than on mental activity. In this instance, it would be pointless for the instructor to assign the student multiple lines each day to memorize the hieroglyph. Since this is a figurative language, the explanation of the hieroglyph and its display in the image or on an interactive board will pique students' attention further. The hieroglyph was a simple pattern with a message in ancient times. The spelling of hieroglyphs became simpler throughout time. Since it is already difficult to see every drawing in every hieroglyph, it is the teacher's responsibility to assist the learner. Using the hieroglyph 火 (huǒ) for fire as an example, we shall examine the topic. The student will develop a clear picture if the teacher makes a card with this hieroglyph: Black fat in mascara, with a flame finished on top. Consider the hieroglyph 木 (mù), which represents a tree.

By placing a crown on top, we are able to create a picture. As a result, youngsters learn to memorize hieroglyphs quickly and readily, and the notion that "Chinese is a fascinating language" does not collapse.

Conclusion. An important point is to summarize at the end of game lessons, a discussion of the difficulties that the guys arose. This contributes to the realization that any game in the lesson is the educational process, which means one of the basic rules is the observance of discipline.

Game lessons very well support the motivation of schoolchildren, children seek to win (which means they are better prepared for the lesson) and learn to work in a team. I would like to finish the article with the Chinese proverb “*Lee Roads begin with one step*”, one should not forget about this either to the teacher or the students.

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